

A 2021 UPDATE ON GREEK ORTHODOX IN AUSTRALIA (Version 2)

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Abstract

The purpose of this report is to document some basic demographic statistics on the 309,963 Greek Orthodox in Australia. This report relies upon the 2021 Census statistics as the most accurate measure of religious affiliation. The report analyses Greek Orthodox by way of age, sex, place of birth and area of residence.

Keywords

Greek Orthodox, Australia, census

INTRODUCTION

This report describes some features of the Greek Orthodox population in Australia. It draws upon the 2021 national Census of Population and Housing and answers questions such as:

- How many people are Greek Orthodox?
- How are the distributed in terms of sex, age, place of birth, or area of residence?

It is an update of an earlier analysis of the 2016 Census date (Athanasou, 2022).

How many people are Greek Orthodox?

In 2021, there were 390,963 Greek Orthodox throughout Australia. While the number of Greek Orthodox has increased from 373,591 in the last Census in 2016, the actual proportion of Greek Orthodox in the population has declined from 1.59% to 1.54%.

Male-Female. There were almost equal numbers of male and female Greek Orthodox in Australia (male = 191,672; female = 199,290).

Age. The age distribution of Greek Orthodox highlights the aging of the population in Australia, in that majority of Greek Orthodox are aged 40 years and over.

Figure 1 compares the proportion in each group for Greek Orthodox with that in the general population. It highlights much lower proportions of Greek Orthodox in the 0-9 years and 20-39 years groups. There is a higher proportion of Greek Orthodox for the 70-79 and 80-89 years age groups. Long-term there will be a demographic effect of the reduced numbers of 0-4 years and 20-39 years.

Figure 1. Greek Orthodox and the total population – a comparison of proportions by 10-year age groups.

Place of Birth. Just on two-thirds of Greek Orthodox (258,453 out of 390,962) were born in Australia (66.1%).

The year of arrival of those Greek Orthodox not born in Australia shows that most arrived in the period 1961-1970 (see Figure 2).

Figure 11. Year of arrival of Greek Orthodox not born in Australia.

Area of residence. Just over 304,938 of the 390,963 Greek Orthodox reside in Victoria (43.6%) and New South Wales (34.3%). The distribution is depicted in Figure 3.

Most Greek Orthodox (91.7%) reside in metropolitan areas rather than non-urban or rural areas (see Table 1), with 122,146 in Greater Sydney and 163,114 in Greater Melbourne. It is only in Queensland where the figure drops to 66% in the capital city area.

Figure 3. Greek Orthodox by State or Territory.

Table 1

Greek Orthodox by capital city area.

Greater capital city	Proportion
Greater Sydney	90.9%
Greater Melbourne	95.6%
Greater Brisbane	66.2%
Greater Adelaide	93.3%
Greater Perth	93.6%
Greater Hobart	77.9%
Greater Darwin	96.0%
Australian Capital Territory	100.0%

SUMMARY

Altogether there are only 390,963 Greek Orthodox in Australia and they make up 1.54% of the population. The nature of the Greek Orthodox population is characterised by:

- almost equal numbers of male and female;
- an aging population with most Greek Orthodox aged 40 years and over;
- a touch under two-thirds of the Greek Orthodox (66%) were born in Australia;

- of those who were not born in Australia, most arrived in the period 1961 to 1970;
- 77.9% of Greek Orthodox reside in Victoria and New South Wales;
- most Greek Orthodox reside in metropolitan areas with 122,146 in Greater Sydney and 163,114 in Greater Melbourne.

No claim is made about the policy implications of these findings but it is reasonable to assume that there should be implications for the planning of Greek Orthodox religious and spiritual services let alone health, education or welfare functions.

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